

CSA Train the Trainers module outline plus supporting materials

Deliverable 2.1

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Please note that the review of this document is still in progress, and the deliverable is subject to final approval. Any feedback or changes provided during this review process may affect the final version, and approval from the relevant parties is required before the deliverable is considered complete.

List of Abbreviations

AKIS	Agricultural Knowledge and Innovation System
ASP	Advisory Service Providers
CoDIE	Co-Design Innovation Experiment
CoP	Community of Practice
CS	Climate Smart
CSA	Climate Smart Advisor
CSC	Climate Smart Coach
CSF	Climate Smart Farming
D	Deliverable
EU	European Union
GHG	Greenhouse gasses
ME&L	Monitoring, Evaluation and Learning
MS	Milestone
NC	National Coordinator
QR-code	Quality Review-code
TTT	Train the Trainers
WP	Work Package

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1 Abstract

The ClimateSmartAdvisors project aims to empower agricultural advisors to support farmers in implementing climate change mitigation and adaptation actions across Europe. The project focuses on boosting the role of agricultural advisors by providing targeted training on climate-smart farming (CSF) practices and facilitating knowledge sharing among advisors. The main vehicle for strengthening advisor capacity are the Communities of Practice (CoP's), comprising a Climate Smart Coach (CSC) and five Climate Smart Advisors (CSA's). The "Train the Trainers" (TTT) programme, designed in collaboration with project partners, aims to build the competence and confidence of the CSC's to lead CoP's and facilitate knowledge exchange.

The training content is designed based on the results of a Training Needs Analysis conducted among Climate Smart Coaches (CSC's). Survey results highlighted the balanced demographic composition of the CSC's, encompassing various levels of expertise and a significant proportion lacking experience in greenhouse gas measurement and climate change vulnerability assessment. Moreover, while familiar with Climate Smart Farming (CSF) concepts, CSC's expressed a need for practical advisory skills, especially in engaging farmers and overcoming resistance to change. Priority thematic areas identified include soil and health biodiversity, crop management, grassland production, and rewarding mechanisms. Based on the survey findings, the TTT programme consists of virtual and in-person sessions covering topics such as soft skills development, establishing and managing CoP's, climate-smart advisory approaches, and planning and monitoring CoP activities. The programme also encompasses a specific thematic session addressing rewarding mechanisms.

Overall, the TTT programme represents a collective effort, integrating inputs and expertise from various project stakeholders and work packages, making the TTT inclusive and comprehensive. By equipping advisors with the necessary knowledge and skills, the project strives to create a network of empowered CSC's capable of driving the adoption of climate-smart farming practices within the European Agricultural Knowledge and Innovation System (AKIS).

2 Introduction

In ClimateSmartAdvisors, advisors are recognised as being in a key position in developing and sharing climate smart (CS) innovations and good practices between peers and with farmers. Therefore, ClimateSmartAdvisors works on improving the opportunities, knowledge, and skills of agricultural advisors to support farmers in the implementation of climate change mitigation and adaptation actions across Europe. The project aims to boost the role of agricultural advisors and advisory service providers (ASP) by strengthening their capacity in providing targeted advice on climate mitigation and adaptation approaches, and by sharing solutions for impactful advisory methods. By boosting the role of the EU agricultural advisory community, we aim to contribute to an acceleration of the adoption of climate smart farming (CSF) practices by the wider farming community within and across EU Agricultural Knowledge and Innovation System (AKIS).

ClimateSmartAdvisors work package (WP) 2 works on the delivery of a CSF “Train the Trainers” (TTT) type training module and supports the delivery of CSF training seminars across partner countries, resulting in an enhancement of the capacity of both current and future farm advisors to empower EU farmers in climate action. Advisors need to update their competencies relating to CSF and utilise them to spread CSF solutions (identified in projects such as ClieNFarms and ClimateFarmDemo), as well as promote new carbon farming opportunities. In successive CoP waves, the project will train CSC’s from across Europe before supporting them as a network to facilitate the delivery of training seminars and workshops to current and future advisors within partner countries. The training interventions will ensure that CSC’s and CSA’s use the knowledge, experience and lessons gained in their professional role with farmers.

This deliverable document contains the module outline and supporting documents for the first TTT programme, to take place in March 2024. It will train a total number of 40 Climate Smart Coaches on a range of relevant advisory skills, including both social skills and technical knowledge. In section 3, it includes a description and summary of Milestone 12, which are the results of a survey among the initial cohort of CSC’s, conducted in late 2023. In sections 4 and 5, as a core of this deliverable, the module outline and storyboards that were developed among all WP2 partners, are presented. Each storyboard contains detailed descriptions on how each module is applied, the timing and organisational aspects including co-facilitators and resources required in order to carry out the various workshop sessions.

3 Results of the Training Needs Analysis

The first TTT within the ClimateSmartAdvisors project will take place in March 2024. Between November and December 2023, a survey was conducted by WP2 of the forty Climate Smart Coaches (CSC's) who registered for the first wave. The purpose of this survey was to capture their needs and tailor the TTT according to those needs. Survey analysis and reporting was conducted by IDELE.

From the survey, it was found:

1. The first wave's panel of CSC's is a well-balanced group in terms of male/female ratios and age range. It has a generally homogenous level of English and covers the full range of technical expertise.
2. However, there appears to be a wide diversity of advisor profiles, from beginners to experienced advisors. In addition, 75% of the registered CSC's have never used a tool to measure GHGs or assess a farm's vulnerability to climate change.
3. Even if the majority of CSC's know what climate smart farming is pretty well, more than half have limited experience in advising farmers in the field. In fact, even those who identified as more confident in this area, expressed a need to find out more.
4. Four thematic areas emerged as priorities in terms of the expectations of CSC's:
 - Soil and health biodiversity
 - Crop management
 - Grassland production
 - Rewarding mechanisms
5. There are high expectations (from all the CSC's) for the TTT regarding learning soft skills to manage their CoP's. No specific priorities emerged as CSC's expressed all categories as a need. From the most important to the least, these are:
 - Motivating a group;
 - At the same level: co-constructing meeting agenda and activities and facilitating discussions;
 - Communicating with the CoP; and
 - At the same level: fostering peer-to-peer learning and delegating responsibility.
6. Specific expectations were expressed regarding the advisor – farmer relationship; specifically how to engage farmers, deal with their negative attitude, and facilitate the transition towards CSF while overcoming the farmers' resistance to change.

The survey results provided important insights to the WP2 team as they developed the TTT programme.

4 TTT objectives and learning outcomes

The objective of the TTT is to build both the competence and confidence of the TTT participants (the CSC's) to lead and facilitate the CoP's across the project lifespan. This deliverable details how this will be achieved.

The design of the TTT was informed by the results of the survey conducted by WP5 (MS12, section 3 above). The training module and material are designed to be used by trainers and to support CSC's in CoP facilitation (WP1), using the knowledge repository (WP5), and connecting to national AKIS actors (WP6). It will also be available in open-access format for use by other trainers through the project website (WP8). The TTT module will be reviewed and updated over time, taking into account the findings from the monitoring and evaluation process (section 8.1). The TTT module will be delivered in a hybrid fashion, including both virtual and in-person elements, and will be delivered on four occasions (coinciding with the start of each COP wave) during the project. Delivery will consist of two virtual sessions (of two hours each), plus three days in-person sessions, for a total of four days contact time. Once trained, the advisors will play a key role as CSC's (WP1), sharing their experiences and providing feedback to improve the training programmes.

On successful completion of this training module, the CSC's should:

- have a better understanding of climate change and climate-smart practices;
- have improved their advisory skills for the provision of climate-smart advice;
- be confident in applying the training content in their advisory practice; and
- be confident in creating an inspiring learning environment facilitating knowledge exchange, learning and capacity building in their respective CoP's.

5 Programme Outline for the Initial TTT

In line with the stated objective, the WP2 team came up with a diversified programme outline to address both the project’s requirements and the expectations of the participants/CSC’s (as identified through the Training Needs Analysis). Table 1 presents a high level overview of the overall programme for the first TTT training course (March 2024), while Table 2 provides a more detailed listing of all of the modules to be included. All presentations and other training resources will be gathered and made available to participants following the TTT.

Table 1: Overall programme for the first TTT (March 2024)

	Overall theme	Date	Time
Online	Zoom		
Day 1 (virtual)	Introduction and about the CSA project	20/02/24	10:00 – 12.00 (CET)
Day 2 (virtual)	Communities of Practice and Climate Smart Farming	08/03/24	13:00 – 15:00 (CET)
In-person	Teagasc College of Amenity Horticulture, Dublin, Ireland		
Day 1	Establishing the COP	19/03/24	12:00 – 18:00
Day 2	Managing the COP	20/03/24	09:00 – 17:00
Day 3	Opportunities and Challenges for Climate Smart Advisory Services	21/03/24	09:00 – 17:00
Day 4	Planning, Monitoring and Beyond the COP	22/03/24	09:00 – 13.00

Table 2: Full programme with description of all TTT modules per day for the first TTT (March 2024)

Day 1 (virtual)	Introduction and about the CSA project			
	Item	Responsibility	Input	Activity
10:00 – 10:15	Welcome and organisational matters	TEAG	Time keeping, programme, technical “house-keeping rules” for Q&A etc.	1
10:15 – 10:25	Introductions	TEAG	Mural whiteboard; map of Europe and everyone places her/his name there; Klaxoon board	2
10:25 – 10:45	Current state of CSA project (with a focus on the role of CSC in the overall project)	ILVO	Presentation	3
10:45 – 11:20	Situation of climate smart advisory services and advisors	IDELE	Presentation, plus participant feedback using Slido or similar; results from the literature research, of the Focus Groups (WP5) and survey (WP1) etc.	4
11:20 – 11:40	Participant expectations of TTT	IDELE	Presentation of results from survey of CSC’s, plus opportunity for further feedback	5
11:40 – 12:00	Outline of programme for remainder of TTT Wrap-up and end	TEAG	Presentation	6

Day 2 (virtual)	Communities of Practice and Climate Smart Farming			
	Item	Responsibility	Input	Activity
13:00 – 13:10	Introduction and recap of Day 1	TEAG	Short presentation	1
13:10 – 13:20	Ice-breaker – Checking in	FüAk	Creative questions to start the sessions	2
13:20 – 14:05	Responsibilities of the CSC and the COP	ILVO	Presentation, plus interactive whiteboard	3
14:05 – 14:50	What is climate smart farming?	IDELE	Interactive whiteboard	4
14:50 – 15:00	Wrap-up and end	TEAG		5

Day 1 (in-person)	Establishing the COP			
	Item	Responsibility	Input	Activity
12:00 – 12:15	Energizer – all who	FüAk	Questions put into the plenum	1
12:15 – 12:30	Welcome and organisational matters	TEAG	Presentation: housekeeping rules, time keeping, programme etc.	2
12:30 – 13:00	Introductions: getting to know each other	FüAk	Cards with visuals	3
13:00 – 13:15	Review of virtual modules	IDELE	Presentation; reflections/ questions from the pre-workshops	4
13:15 – 14:15	Lunch break			
14:15 – 15:45	Managing the CoP (recruitment of members, organising the first meeting, agreeing ground rules, selecting focus area(s), building a common understanding etc.)	UZEI/ILVO (WP2 partner to present)	Guidelines for COP's (MS1); facilitated workshop	5
15:45 – 16:15	Presentation of group results	TEAG		6
16:15 – 16:30	Coffee/tea break			
16:30 – 16:45	Energizer - showing group vs. individual knowledge	TEAG	Handout for exercise	7
16:45 – 18:10	Facilitation Training (Part 1, what is facilitation, how to facilitate a group/CoP)	FüAk/TEAG	Refer to CECRA module More introductory level than Part 2	8
18:10 – 18:15	Evaluation of the day and mentimeter exercise		Evaluation form and QR-code	

Day 1 (in-person)	Evening activity			
	Item	Responsibility	Input	Activity
19:30	Social dinner			

Day 2 (in-person)	Managing the COP			
	Item	Responsibility	Input	Activity
09:00 – 09:15	Energizer - active listening (I am going to the market)	FüAk	Participatory creation of a story for memory	1
09:15 – 09:45	Feedback from Facilitation (Part 1)	TEAG/FüAk		2
09:45 – 11:15	Facilitation (Part 2, encouraging participation, promoting creativity and supporting decision making, managing the CoP, identification of training needs for CoP)	IDELE/SZE	Refer to CECRA module Facilitation approaches for different phases of the CoP (MS1) Workshop(s)- identification/prioritisation of CoP activities/training needs	3
11:15 – 11:30	Coffee/tea break			
11:30 – 12:00	Feedback from Facilitation (Part 2)	SZE		4
12:00 – 13:00	Dealing with challenging situations in CoP's, and creating trust	FüAk	"Fish bowl" exercise	5
13:00 – 14:00	Lunch break			
14:00 – 14:30	Dealing with challenging situations in CoP's – feedback	FüAk	"Fish bowl" exercise	6
14:30 – 15:30	Prioritising climate mitigation and adaptation practices relevant for farming in your region	TEAG	WP5 and CFD Knowledge Repository; list of potential climate solutions printed on cards; decision matrix; refer to ClieNFarms workshop	7
15:30 – 15:45	Coffee/tea break			
15:45 – 16:15	Feedback and identification of priority mitigation and adaptation measures	TEAG		8
16:15 – 17:00	Reducing barriers and finding solutions to increase the uptake of mitigation and adaptation practices (and the provision of climate advisory services)	TEAG	Priority measures from previous session	9
17:00 – 17:10	Evaluation of the day and mentimeter exercise	WR	Evaluation form and QR-code	10

Day 3 (in-person)	Opportunities and Challenges for Climate Smart Advisory Services			
	Item	Responsibility	Input	Activity
09:00 – 09:15	Energizer – Alternative use of objects	FüAk	Question and Answers	1
09:15 – 10:00	Recap of Day 2, focusing on key learnings	TEAG		2
10:00 – 11:00	How change happens on farm: understanding the learning journey for both the CSA and farmer; and motivating farmers	IDELE	Learning journey displayed on a screen	3
11:00 – 11:15	Coffee/tea break			
11:15 – 12:15	The role of diagnostic tools through CoP activities	IDELE	Diagnostic tools	4
12:15 – 12:30	Film on CO2 emission calculator	FüAk	Film	5
12:30 – 13:30	Lunch break			
13:30 – 14:30	The potential for win-win solutions and rewarding mechanisms	BOERENBOND	Rewarding mechanisms thematic	6
14:30 – 14:45	Coffee/tea break			
14:45 – 16:15	Advisory approaches: focussing on working with other AKIS actors to increase the uptake of climate solutions, including case study examples from Scotland and Ireland	FüAk/SZE SRUC TEAG	WP6: Network Analysis – exercise – WHO (outside of CoP) Farming for a Better Climate (SRUC) - presentation, 15 mins Signpost Programme (TEAG) – presentation, 15 mins	7
16:15 – 16:30	Evaluation of the day and mentimeter exercise	WR	Evaluation form and mentimeter QR-code	

Day 4 (in-person)	Planning, Monitoring and Beyond the CoP			
	Item	Responsibility	Input	Activity
09:00 – 09:15	Energizer - My North	FüAk	Group exercise in the plenum	1
09:15 – 09:45	Guidelines for CSA Training Seminars and Events	SRUC	MS21 Presentation	2
09:45 – 11:00	How will you know that the CoP is functioning well?: monitoring progress	WR	MS1 MS7 and MS26 Presentation	3
11:00 – 11:15	Coffee/tea break			
11:15 – 12:30	Creating a CoP Plan	WP1 (Martin, guidelines)	CSA CoP template (WP1) Short presentation, followed by time for participants to beginning drafting their CoP Plan	4
12:30 – 13:00	Conclusion and final feedback (key learnings and questions remaining)	TEAG		5
13:00 – 13:10	Last mentimeter and reminder to complete final evaluation	WR	Link and instructions	6

Note: this is the state of the full programme as of February 14th 2024. It is subject to minor modifications prior to March 19th, 2024.

6 Collaboration with other WP partners

The detailed and full programme was developed in close collaboration with other WP partners in the CSA project, in order to involve their specific expertise. Firstly, a number of guidelines, which also represent milestones in the CSA project, were developed by CSA partners; these guidelines are summarised in Table 3. In addition to WP2 partners (who have responsibility for this deliverable and the design and delivery of the TTT) the guidelines listed in Table 3 were developed across three other WP's (WP 1, 4 and 5). Meetings were held with relevant CSA partners to agree where the guidelines best fit in the TTT programme, and to mutually support the timely achievement of milestones and D2.1.

Table 3: CSA Milestones integrated into TTT

MS No.	Milestone	WP	Responsibility
1	Guidelines for CoP's and knowledge exchange on CoP, national and European level	1	EV ILVO
7	Evaluation tools for CoP's and European knowledge exchange ready	4	WR
21	Guidelines for CSA Training Seminars/Events	2	SRUC
26	ME&L integrated in CoP's, TTT, CoDIEs	4	WR
42	Guidelines for CoP's to test tools and methods in the repository	5	IDELE

Further, the TTT organisers and program designers also collaborated with the technical leader on rewarding mechanisms (BOERENBOND) in order to plan together the session "The potential for win: win solutions and rewarding mechanisms" on Day 3.

Last but not least, the TTT is indeed an outcome of the close collaboration between WP2 and WP5. WP5 is tasked to create a knowledge repository of many different advisory tools and methods. The methods which have been chosen for the TTT are also the content of the first pilot repository that is being developed in parallel. In addition, all methods of the TTT are described in a WP5 booklet, which will be distributed to all participants at the first TTT in March 2024.

As such, the final programme developed continuously into a collective product that includes the expertise, knowledge and methodological competence of many work packages and representatives of CSA. This makes this TTT particularly inclusive and bears high potential of equipping participants with new knowledge but also the motivation and tailored resources to implement what they will have learnt. Involving professionals from more than one institution and work package bears higher chances that the content will be well adopted by different institutional and research settings.

7 Module Content/Storyboards

This section lists all the different storyboards (in total) that make up the TTT programme of the first CoP wave.

7.1 Storyboards for Online Day 1

Name of session		The Climate Smart Advisors project and the role of the CoP's				Activity no. 3
Time		10:25 – 10:45				
Session objective		The objective(s) of this training module (session) is to: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • provide a short overview of the project • explain the central role of the CoP's and the CSC's in the project <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • explain the project definition of a "climate smart advisor" 				
Session learning outcomes		On successful completion of this training module (session), participants will be able to: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • understand the role of the CoP activities in relation to other project activities • understand their responsibilities for being a CSC <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • know the definition of a climate smart advisor 				
Time	Theme	Objective/key learnings/attitudes	Activity (both for the facilitator and the participants)	Who/Facilitator and Co-facilitator	Resources/Material	Documentation
Pre-day 1 10:25 – 10:40	The Climate Smart Advisors project and the role of CoP's	See above	Presentation on: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Brief introduction of the overall project activities • Explanation of the role of CoP's and CSC's in the project Definition of Climate Smart Advisors	Laure/Lies	PPT	
Pre-day 1 10:40 – 10:45	Q&A		Ask whether there are some questions based on the presentations	Laure/Lies		

Name of session		Situation of climate smart advisory services and advisors				Activity no. 4
Time		10:45 – 11:20				
Session objective		<p>The objective(s) of this training module (session) is to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • present the first results from different WPs in the project : insights from focus groups (WP5), online survey (WP1) and literature review • discuss them 				
Session learning outcomes		<p>On successful completion of this training module (session), participants will be able to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • have a global overview of the situation of climate smart advisory services in the European countries of the project • reflect on his/her own position and country situation in this context 				
Time	Theme	Objective/key learnings/attitudes	Activity (both for the facilitator and the participants)	Who/Facilitator and Co-facilitator	Resources/Material	Documentation
Pre-day 1 9.45 – 10.05			Presentation	Florence	PPT	
Pre-day 1 10.05 – 10.20			Sticky notes to position on various aspects	Florence	Interactive white board (klaxoon?)	

Name of session		Participants expectations of TTT				Activity no. 5
Time		11:20 – 11:40				
Session objective		The objective(s) of this training module (session) is to: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • present the results of the survey of CSC's (10 min) • add and discuss according to eventual new needs (national meeting...) • tell them what to expect 				
Session learning outcomes		On successful completion of this training module (session), participants will be able to: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • have in mind the expectations of the others and can update his/her own expectations • knows which of the expectations can be fulfilled in the TTT among those expressed 				
Time	Theme	Objective/key learnings/attitudes	Activity (both for the facilitator and the participants)	Who/Facilitator and Co-facilitator	Resources/Material	Documentation
Pre-day 1 11:20 – 11:30			Presentation	Florence	PPT	
Pre-day 1 11:30 – 11:40			Also ask them to bring their tools like Jenga blocks, card games for advising for the TTT	Florence I	Interactive white board	

7.2 Storyboards for Online Day 2

Name of session		Energizer: “Checking in”				No.2
Time		13:10 – 13:20				
Session objective		The objective(s) of this training module (session) is to: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • warm-up and get started for the day • show a method to get in the mood for the day with targeted questions 				
Session learning outcomes		On successful completion of this training module (session), participants will be able to: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • start relaxed and concentrated into the meeting 				
Time	Theme	Objective/key learnings/attitudes	Activity (both for the facilitator and the participants)	Who/Facilitator and Co-facilitator	Resources/Material	Documentation
Pre-day 2 13:10 – 13:20	“Checking in”: How to start a digital meeting with creative Check-in questions	Participants are aware of how to get in the mood for the day’s questions and topics;	<u>Before the meeting.</u> Slides with 6 questions: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. To make the day more mindful, I will... 2. Which word should we use less often today? 3. Which superpower would you like to have today? 4. How can we make today a perfect day? 5. To make today more curious, I will... 6. What is the most pointless thing you have to do today? <u>In the meeting:</u> The facilitator asks the questions; the participants have approx.. 10 seconds to think; the facilitator chooses a participant at random, who answers the facilitator then ask the next question and selects another participant and so on.	Ingeborg, Annelie	Slides with questions Names of the Zoom-participants;	None

Name of session		The responsibilities of the CoP's and CSC's			Activity No. 3	
Time		13:30 – 14:05				
Session objective		<p>The objective(s) of this training module (session) is to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • explain what a CoP in Climate Smart Advisors is • explain the role and responsibilities of the CSC's • explain the opportunities and limitations of a running a CoP within ClimateSmartAdvisors 				
Session learning outcomes		<p>On successful completion of this training module (session), participants will be able to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • understand what a CoP within ClimateSmartAdvisors is • understand their role and responsibilities as a coach of a CoP • understand the possibilities for managing a CoP within ClimateSmartAdvisors 				
Time	Theme	Objective/key learnings/attitudes	Activity (both for the facilitator and the participants)	Who/Facilitator and Co-facilitator	Resources/Material	Documentation
Pre-day 2 13:20 – 14:05	The responsibilities of the CoP's and the CSC's	See above	<p>1. Presentation with:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - A clear definition of a CoP in CSA - Explain the expectations and limitations of the CoP's within the project - Explain the role of a CSC, based on the CSC journey in the project 	Laure/Martin	PPT	
			<p>2. interactive exercise in Klaxoon/Mural, in which CSC's are asked to highlight the tasks in their journey they are most and least confident about.</p>	Laure/Martin	Klaxoon board	
			<p>3. PPT on the practicalities related to managing a CoP:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - recruitment of CSA's - budget - reporting 	Laure/Martin	PPT.	

Name of session		What is Climate Smart Farming?				Activity No. 4
Time		14:05 – 14:50				
Session objective		<p>The objective(s) of this training module (session) is to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • transfer a common understanding of Climate-smart farming • start the reflection of its CoP positioning related to CSF • show a method in order to address this question in a group – as can be done in the CoP 				
Session learning outcomes		<p>On successful completion of this training module (session), participants will be able to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • be aware of the necessity to define CSF at the beginning of the CoP and have some first tools and notions to address and discuss it in the CoP 				
Time	Theme	Objective/key learnings/attitudes	Activity (both for the facilitator and the participants)	Who/Facilitator and Co-facilitator	Resources/Material	Documentation
Pre-day 2 14:05 – 14:15			Word cloud + standard definition	Caroline	Klaxoon or other	Document summing up with Klaxoon screenshot
Pre-day 2 14:15 – 14:25			2- 3 testimonies	Benoit + team, Niamh, Riina		
Pre-day 2 14:25 – 14:35			Each person tries to formulate its vision for CSFarming in their context (written + sharing orally afterwards) + what it means for the directions (awareness raising, ...) to develop/take in advisory	4 groups of 10 CSC's: facilitators needed!	Klaxoon or other -> 4 spaces defined on the whiteboard, one for each group	
Pre-day 2 14:35 – 14:50		Start imagining this in your CoP	Plan on how to discuss this in your CoP : you have seen and heard the diversity of how to understand this theme of CSF -> please keep it in mind and for inspiration when starting your own CoP			

7.3 Storyboards for In-Person Day 1

Name of session		Energizer: all who...				Activity no. 1
Time		12:00 – 12:15				
Session objective		The objective(s) of this training module (session) is to: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> warm-up the participants and creating a relaxed atmosphere 				
Session learning outcomes		On successful completion of this training module (session), participants will be able to: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> use a simple energizer to start a meeting with a large number of participants 				
Time	Theme	Objective/key learnings/attitudes	Activity (both for the facilitator and the participants)	Who/Facilitator and Co-facilitator	Resources/Material	Documentation
Day 1 12:00 – 12:15	Energizer: “All those who...”	Participants are aware of how a relaxed atmosphere is created in a large plenary session at the beginning of the meeting, when the participants do not yet know each other	The facilitator asks questions, the participants stand up when they are affected. Questions: 1. All those who have been to a pub yesterday evening 2. Everyone who wears colourful socks 3. Anyone who doesn`t know Teagasc 4. Anyone who knows an Irish pub song 5. Anyone who sings, now sing an Irish pub song to welcome the participants	Annelie, Ingeborg	None	None

Name of session		Introductions: getting to know each other				Activity 3
Time		12:30 – 13:00				
Session objective		The objective(s) of this training module (session) is to <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • get people to introduce each other in a playful way • get people to think in a creative way about their involvement in CSA 				
Session learning outcomes		On successful completion of this training module (session), participants will be able to: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • know each other better and feel more familiar with the workshop setting and participants 				
In the remainder of the table below, list your sequential plan of action for the module (session) that will allow you to deliver on your session objective.						
Time	Theme	Objective/key learnings/attitudes	Activity (both for the facilitator and the participants)	Who/Facilitator and Co-facilitator	Resources/Material	Documentation
Day 1 12:30 – 12:35	Getting to know each other	Participants get to know other participants, their level of experience and involvement with CSA	<u>Before the exercise:</u> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Divide participants in groups of 6 people 2. Each group will be assigned to a table where 6-8 visual cards are lying down. 3. Explain the exercise 	Annelie, Ingeborg	6 tables in 6 separate spaces, cards with visuals that invite participants to think creatively (trees, nature objects, networks, other things), to be bought by FÜAK beforehand.	Photographs
Day 1 12:35 – 13.00			<u>Start the exercise:</u> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. One person in the group starts picking a card and says his or her name, country, how the picture relates to his/her involvement as a CSA, expectations and experience 2. The next person picks a card and so on. 3. Each person speaks for about 2 minutes. Total time in group: 12-14 minutes 4. Then the people move on to other tables, so they get mixed with as many people as possible 			

Name of session		Review of pre-workshop				Activity No.4
Time		13:00 – 13:15				
Session objective		The objective(s) of this training module (session) is to: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • see what people remember from the pre-days • collect unanswered questions 				
Session learning outcomes		On successful completion of this training module (session), participants will be able to: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • know the “fridge” method for pending questions and will be able to use it 				
Time	Theme	Objective/key learnings/attitudes	Activity (both for the facilitator and the participants)	Who/Facilitator and Co-facilitator	Resources/Material	Documentation
Day 1 13.00 – 13.15	review of preworkshop		4 paper boards hanging – ask people to put sticky notes on them with their ideas. For each: What do you remember? What did you learn? Pending questions to write in the fridge. Afterwards the facilitators move the questions in 2 categories : “we will address them in the TTT” OR “we need to see how and if we can address them”.	Caroline, Florence	4 Paperboards hanging on the wall : one per “big” session of the pre-days : <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Current state of CSA project - Situation of CS Advisory services in Europe - Building understanding of the CoP - Definition of Climate Smart Farming 2 paperboards for the fridge. Sticky notes – at least 5 per person	

Name of session		Managing the CoP's				Activity no. 5 and 6
Time		14:15 – 16:15				
Session objective		<p>The objective(s) of this training module (session) is to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • remind the CSC's about their responsibilities with their CoP • make them familiar with the guidelines for CoP management • provide them with the competences to draft their CoP objectives and CoP plan during their first CoP meeting 				
Session learning outcomes		<p>On successful completion of this training module (session), participants will be able to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • understand their responsibilities for CoP management • know where to find the guidelines for CoP management • facilitate their first CoP meeting to develop the learning questions, CoP objectives and the CoP plan 				
Time	Theme	Objective/key learnings/attitudes	Activity (both for the facilitator and the participants)	Who/Facilitator and Co-facilitator	Resources/Material	Documentation
Day 1 14:15 – 14:30	CSC responsibilities	Remind the CSC's about their responsibilities with their CoP	<p>Presentation:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Short summary of what was presented during the pre-days. - Provide an overview of the CoP guidelines and where to find them - Show which aspect of the CSC journey this session will deal with - Introduce the CoP template 	Laure/Martin via online call	Presentation	CoP guidelines
Day 1 14:30 – 14:45	First CoP meeting	Introduce them into the script for the first CoP meeting	<p>Presentation:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Introducing ground rules for the CoP (we give them some suggestions) - Develop learning questions and objectives - Develop a CoP plan - Explain the exercise 			
Day 1 14:45 – 15:45	Exercise to practice the formulation of ground rules learning questions and objectives	Practice the formulation of CoP objectives	<p>The participants are divided into groups of 5-6 people. Their task is to build a CoP of CSC's. They have to:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Agree upon the ground rules within the CoP. A basic set of ground rules is given. They have to adapt and/or complete this list (10 min) 			

Name of session		Managing the CoP's				Activity no. 5 and 6
Time		14:15 – 16:15				
Session objective		<p>The objective(s) of this training module (session) is to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • remind the CSC's about their responsibilities with their CoP • make them familiar with the guidelines for CoP management • provide them with the competences to draft their CoP objectives and CoP plan during their first CoP meeting 				
Session learning outcomes		<p>On successful completion of this training module (session), participants will be able to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • understand their responsibilities for CoP management • know where to find the guidelines for CoP management • facilitate their first CoP meeting to develop the learning questions, CoP objectives and the CoP plan 				
Time	Theme	Objective/key learnings/attitudes	Activity (both for the facilitator and the participants)	Who/Facilitator and Co-facilitator	Resources/Material	Documentation
			<p>2. Think about challenges they will experience for managing their CoP and select 3 (15 min)</p> <p>3. Formulate learning questions they have regarding CoP management related to these challenges and select 3. (15 min)</p> <p>4. Translate the learning questions in SMART objectives for the CoP of Coaches (20 min)</p>			
Day 1 15:45 – 16:15	Feedback from groups		<p>Ask participants to stand on a scale of difficult with the left side of the room being difficult and the right side of the room being easy: How did they experience the formulation of:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - ground rules - learning questions - SMART objectives <p>After each question ask a couple of people to explain:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Why they thought it was easy or difficult. (15 min) 2. Ask each group to share 1 objective. Each next group is not allowed to share the same 			

Name of session		Managing the CoP's			Activity no. 5 and 6	
Time		14:15 – 16:15				
Session objective		<p>The objective(s) of this training module (session) is to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • remind the CSC's about their responsibilities with their CoP • make them familiar with the guidelines for CoP management • provide them with the competences to draft their CoP objectives and CoP plan during their first CoP meeting 				
Session learning outcomes		<p>On successful completion of this training module (session), participants will be able to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • understand their responsibilities for CoP management • know where to find the guidelines for CoP management • facilitate their first CoP meeting to develop the learning questions, CoP objectives and the CoP plan 				
Time	Theme	Objective/key learnings/attitudes	Activity (both for the facilitator and the participants)	Who/Facilitator and Co-facilitator	Resources/Material	Documentation
			objective than what was already shared. When another group has a similar objective as the one shared, this group shouts "BINGO"! Start another round until all SMART objectives are shared. (15 min)			

Name of session		Energizer, showing group vs. individual knowledge			Activity no. 7	
Time		16:30 – 16:45				
Session objective		The objective(s) of this training module (session) is to: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> warm-up the participants and creating a relaxed atmosphere 				
Session learning outcomes		On successful completion of this training module (session), participants will be able to: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> use a simple energizer to start a meeting with a large number of participants 				
Time	Theme	Objective/key learnings/attitudes	Activity (both for the facilitator and the participants)	Who/Facilitator and Co-facilitator	Resources/Material	Documentation
Day 1 16:30 – 16:45	Energizer, showing group vs individual knowledge	Participants should see that combining individual knowledge into a group increases the groups ability to answer questions when compared to an individual	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Participants will be split into groups Randomly select one individual from each group Individuals are taken into a separate room and spaced apart Groups and individuals are given the prepared quiz, they are asked not to flip it over till the timer starts. Time the groups and individuals while completing the quiz for approx. 5 minutes Once complete have everyone re-enter the same room. Get the individuals and the groups to swap the quizzes so they correct each other's. Once corrected gather the results and display them on the whiteboard Usually the group results are better than the individual results 	Niamh, Tom	Pens, prepared handout with logos and puzzles	

Name of session		Facilitation, part 1			Activity 8 and Activity 2 (Feedback on day 2, Activity 2)	
Time		16:45 – 18:10 and 09:15 – 09:45 on day 2				
Session objective		The objective(s) of this training module (session) is to: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • make future advisors aware of the importance of facilitation in a COP and equip them with the basics of facilitation 				
Session learning outcomes		On successful completion of this training module (session), participants will be able to: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • differentiate between good and bad facilitation practices • carry a basic understanding of facilitation into the 2nd session of facilitation where participants learn specific facilitation methods 				
Time	Theme	Objective/key learnings/attitudes	Activity (both for the facilitator and the participants)	Who/Facilitator and Co-facilitator	Resources/Material	Documentation
Day 1	Facilitation-introduction and basics	Participants are aware of the significance and importance of facilitation in a CoP. Importance of working in small groups and first let them work then comment, importance of having everyone speak	Group work exercise	Annelie, Ingeborg	Large sheets of paper, pens, 6 separate areas for accommodating groups	Photo story, protocol etc.
Day 1 16:45 – 17:15			Group work with 3 questions: 1. What is facilitation? Why is facilitation important in CoP activities? 2. What makes a good facilitator/facilitation session (incl. good and bad practices/tips and tricks) 3 What to take into account as a CoP leader when facilitating? Each question addressed by 2 groups. (ca. 6 people per group)			photo story, protocol etc.

Name of session		Facilitation, part 1			Activity 8 and Activity 2 (Feedback on day 2, Activity 2)	
Time		16:45 – 18:10 and 09:15 – 09:45 on day 2				
Session objective		The objective(s) of this training module (session) is to: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • make future advisors aware of the importance of facilitation in a COP and equip them with the basics of facilitation 				
Session learning outcomes		On successful completion of this training module (session), participants will be able to: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • differentiate between good and bad facilitation practices • carry a basic understanding of facilitation into the 2nd session of facilitation where participants learn specific facilitation methods 				
Time	Theme	Objective/key learnings/attitudes	Activity (both for the facilitator and the participants)	Who/Facilitator and Co-facilitator	Resources/Material	Documentation
Day 1 17:15 – 17:35			Presentation on what is facilitation and three types of conversation Round Table, Discussion and Conference (RDK) and back to groups	Annelie and Ingeborg		
Day 1 17:40 – 18:10			Back to groups and exercise on RDK	Annelie and Ingeborg, further co-facilitators needed.		

7.4 Storyboards for In-Person Day 2

Name of session		Energizer: I am going to the market			Activity no.1	
Time		09:00 – 09:15				
Session objective		The objective(s) of this training module (session) is to: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> energize and to warm-up for the meeting on day 2 make active listening conscious 				
Session learning outcomes		On successful completion of this training module (session), participants will be able to: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> start relaxed and with a higher energy-level to the meeting pay full attention to the person speaking and actively respond to them recognise the importance of following the speaker attentively 				
Time	Theme	Objective/key learnings/attitudes	Activity (both for the facilitator and the participants)	Who/Facilitator and Co-facilitator	Resources/Material	Documentation
Day 2 09:00 – 09:15	Energizer: an active listening game	The participants experience that a playful start to a meeting is positive. They are aware that active listening means memorising information from the course of the conversation and using it to improve the quality of the conversation to his interlocutor	<p><u>Before the meeting:</u> Seating for 6 rooms or enclosed areas for 7 people; seating in a circle. Facilitators divide the 40 participants into 6 subgroups of 7 people each, shown on a slide.</p> <p><u>In the meeting:</u> The facilitator explains the rules of the game: One person starts by saying “I am going to the market to buy fish”. The next person says “I am going to the market to buy fish and potatoes”. Each person repeats the list, and then adds an item. The aim is to be able to remember all of the items that all of the people before you have listed. If one person makes a mistake, the next person starts with a new sentence, e. g. “For my trip to the seaside I put my swimming costume in my suitcase”. The next person says “For my trip.....swimming costume and sun cream in my suitcase”. And so on. Then the participants return to the plenum.</p>	Annelie, Ingeborg All participants take part	<p><u>Rooms or enclosed areas:</u> 6 with 7 chairs each</p> <p><u>Slides:</u> Brief explanation and visualisation of the game. Categorisation of the subgroups allocated rooms</p>	None

Name of session		Facilitation part 2, encouraging participation, promoting creativity, and supporting decision making, managing the CoP's, identification of training needs for CoP's				Activity no. 3 and 4
Time		09:45 – 11:15 and 11:30 – 12:00				
Session objective		<p>The objective(s) of this training module (session) is to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> introduce participants to a range of creative facilitation methods for CoP's based on the principles of learning by doing. focus on methods that help with decision making and think creatively in a COP on successful completion of this training module (session), participants will be able to: apply different facilitation methods and know which method is best suited for which occasion in a CoP lifetime/meeting 				
Session learning outcomes		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> on successful completion of this training module (session), participants will be able to: apply different facilitation methods and know which method is best suited for which occasion in a CoP lifetime/meeting 				
Time	Theme	Objective/key learnings/ attitudes	Activity (both for the facilitator and the participants)	Who/Facilitator and Co-facilitator	Resources/Material	Documentation
Day 2 9.45 – 10.00	Introduction		<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Explain the session Let people go around the posters and chose two methods, they would like to experiment Based on the selection, make 4 groups 	The facilitators have in advance prepared questions linked to the CoP's activity (identification of training needs, chose CoP thematic, explore new solutions, chose tool to test...)	Posters hanging in the main room : one per facilitation method. 2 main themes: - promote creativity - Support decision making (ideas of methods: see below) coloured sticky notes	
Day 2 10.00 – 11.15	Experience it		In each of the 4 groups : make 2 sub groups 15 minutes to prepare a facilitation session in each subgroup in parallel 30 minutes for each subgroup to make its session + feedback of participants on advantages and disadvantages of the method	4 facilitators needed (Caroline, Florence, Andras + 1) requirement: each one is comfortable with all the methods	"observation sheet"	
Day 2 11:15 – 11.30	Coffee/tea break					
Day 2 11:30 – 12.00	Feedback session		Participants discuss their observations in 4 groups (10 people per group). We ask for a short summary from each group. We ask what methods they used and what their experiences were. Highlight the pearls and puzzles.	4 facilitators (Caroline, Florence, Andras + 1)	Moderation cards, pin wands	

Name of session		Facilitation part 2, encouraging participation, promoting creativity, and supporting decision making, managing the CoP's, identification of training needs for CoP's				Activity no. 3 and 4
Time		09:45 – 11:15 and 11:30 – 12:00				
Session objective		<p>The objective(s) of this training module (session) is to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> introduce participants to a range of creative facilitation methods for CoP's based on the principles of learning by doing. focus on methods that help with decision making and think creatively in a COP on successful completion of this training module (session), participants will be able to: apply different facilitation methods and know which method is best suited for which occasion in a CoP lifetime/meeting 				
Session learning outcomes		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> on successful completion of this training module (session), participants will be able to: apply different facilitation methods and know which method is best suited for which occasion in a CoP lifetime/meeting 				
Time	Theme	Objective/key learnings/ attitudes	Activity (both for the facilitator and the participants)	Who/Facilitator and Co-facilitator	Resources/Material	Documentation
			<p>Participants have 10 minutes to discuss and write their experiences on a moderation card. Facilitators will help participants with the following questions:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Which facilitation technique did you find most useful? Why? - Have there been instances where a facilitation technique was particularly effective or challenging to use? - What was the most significant lesson learned for the group/CoP from this session? - Is there an area where further development is needed in terms of facilitation skills? <p>These are just supporting questions. The 4 facilitators can change the questions depending on the dynamics of the group. When 10 minutes have passed, one of the participants in the group presents the "results" and sticks them on the pin wall. Each group has 5 minutes to do this.</p>			

Choice of methods

- Brainstorming with sticky notes
- World café <https://www.sessionlab.com/methods/world-cafe> or carrousel <https://www.sessionlab.com/methods/carousel>
- Photo language
- The six thinking Bono hats <https://www.sessionlab.com/methods/the-six-thinking-hats>
- Bridge to the future
- PSAI (problem/solution/advantages/disadvantages)
- Coaching by peers
- Devils or angel's advocate <https://www.benlinders.com/2011/devils-or-angels-advocate-which-role-do-you-prefer/>
- Autumn leaves

Name of session		Dealing with challenging situations in CoP's, and creating trust				Activity No. 5 and 6
Time		12:00 – 13:00 and 14:00 – 14:30				
Session objective		<p>The objective(s) of this training module (session) is to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • be aware of the problems and challenging situations to be expected • find solutions to deal with problems/challenging situations • build trust • get to know the fishbowl method 				
Session learning outcomes		<p>On successful completion of this training module (session), participants will be able to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • try the fishbowl method • know and deal with challenging situations in a CoP 				
Time	Theme	Objective/key learnings/attitudes	Activity (both for the facilitator and the participants)	Who/Facilitator and Co-facilitator	Resources/Material	Documentation
Day 2 12:00 – 12:10	Dealing with challenging situations in CoP's, and creating trust; feedback	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Participants recognize the challenging situations in a CoP, - they look for and find solutions. - Participants work in a large group - Participants reflect the method and the possible uses 	<p>Before the meeting Form an inner circle with 8 chairs, then a circle with 14 chairs and behind a circle with 18 chairs, Prepare a digital template with the categories for the challenging situation and the solutions.</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. personal level, 2. methodological level, 3. technical level, 4. other. 	Annelie, Ingeborg and others. Two people facilitate, one writes down the contributions for documentation	A large room, 43 (?) chairs, a large screen (or two, depends on the room), to be able to read the documentation Pinboard, dots	
Day 2 12:10 – 12:20			<p><u>Explain the rules and instructions:</u> The participants sit down, one chair in the inner circle remains free.</p> <p><u>Work instructions/ rules</u></p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Only the participants in the inner circle of chairs are allowed to speak. 2. Only one person speaks at a time. 			

Name of session		Dealing with challenging situations in CoP's, and creating trust				Activity No. 5 and 6
Time		12:00 – 13:00 and 14:00 – 14:30				
Session objective		<p>The objective(s) of this training module (session) is to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • be aware of the problems and challenging situations to be expected • find solutions to deal with problems/challenging situations • build trust • get to know the fishbowl method 				
Session learning outcomes		<p>On successful completion of this training module (session), participants will be able to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • try the fishbowl method • know and deal with challenging situations in a CoP 				
Time	Theme	Objective/key learnings/attitudes	Activity (both for the facilitator and the participants)	Who/Facilitator and Co-facilitator	Resources/Material	Documentation
			<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 3. If you want to join the discussion from the outside circle, you have to sit on the free chair. 4. Those who no longer want to or can no longer contribute from the inner circle switch to one of the outer circles. 			
Day 2 12:20 – 12:40			Start the session with the following question: “what challenging situations can occur in CoP’s?”			Photographs
12:40 – 13:00			What solutions could you imagine for each of the challenges you can see on the cards written? Summarising the results and highlighting the most important points			
LUNCH BREAK						
Day 2 14:00 – 14:30			<p>Participants give feedback on the fishbowl method</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. with coloured dots on a pinboard. the choices are: I thought it was “very good”, “good”, “not good”: Everyone gets one point to distribute. 2. contribution from the plenum 			

Name of session		Prioritising climate mitigation and adaptation practices relevant for farming in your region			Activity no. 7 and 8	
Time		14:30 – 15:10 and 15:25 – 15:45				
Session objective		<p>The objective(s) of this training module (session) is to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • increase awareness of the range of available climate mitigation and adaptation measures; • explore the potential contribution that different climate solutions can make; • provide participants with a framework to allow them to identify the most relevant climate solutions for their region or country. 				
Session learning outcomes		<p>On successful completion of this training module (session), participants will be able to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • prioritise potential climate mitigation and adaptation solutions relevant for farming in their region. 				
Time	Theme	Objective/key learnings/ attitudes	Activity (both for the facilitator and the participants)	Who/Facilitator and Co-facilitator	Resources/Material	Documentation
Day 2 14:30 – 14:40	Climate mitigation and adaptation practices		<p>Short presentation about:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • WP5 and CDF knowledge repository • The CFD webinar (as a source of content/materials) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ The slides include one slide with two questions: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Who joined the CFD webinar on 9th February? ○ What were the main lessons for you from the webinar? • The potential climate solutions that will be used in the next activities 	Tom, Niamh	Presentation	
Day 2 14:40 – 14:55	Climate mitigation and adaptation practices		<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Participants will be split into 4 groups of 10 participants 2. Each participant will get a set of ~ 10 printed cards with solutions (everyone in the group will have the same solutions) 3. Participants will be invited to discuss the solutions based on their likelihood of implementation <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a) The participants should write on blank box on each of their cards a score 	Tom, Niamh Help will be required by other facilitators to guide each group.	Flip chart, markers, Pre-printed cards with solutions, printed impact level of the solutions list	Example of solution card below (Figure 1)

Name of session		Prioritising climate mitigation and adaptation practices relevant for farming in your region			Activity no. 7 and 8	
Time		14:30 – 15:10 and 15:25 – 15:45				
Session objective		<p>The objective(s) of this training module (session) is to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • increase awareness of the range of available climate mitigation and adaptation measures; • explore the potential contribution that different climate solutions can make; • provide participants with a framework to allow them to identify the most relevant climate solutions for their region or country. 				
Session learning outcomes		<p>On successful completion of this training module (session), participants will be able to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • prioritise potential climate mitigation and adaptation solutions relevant for farming in their region. 				
Time	Theme	Objective/key learnings/ attitudes	Activity (both for the facilitator and the participants)	Who/Facilitator and Co-facilitator	Resources/Material	Documentation
			<p>between 1 (low) and 10 (high) of what they think is the likelihood of implementation in their country.</p> <p>b) The participants will then place cards along the provided line going from low to high likelihood of implementation.</p> <p>c) Since likelihood of implementation will be different between the countries this is very based on the participants knowledge</p> <p>4. Once all solutions are on the line. Ask participants to write in the second black box on the solution card the rank of the solutions from 1 = least impact to 10 = most impact on carbon footprint based on their own assessment.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The facilitator will be provided with a list of all solutions ranked on 1 = least impact to 10 = most impact so they can help guide the participants with this ranking <p>5. Take photo of the line</p>			

Name of session		Prioritising climate mitigation and adaptation practices relevant for farming in your region			Activity no. 7 and 8	
Time		14:30 – 15:10 and 15:25 – 15:45				
Session objective		<p>The objective(s) of this training module (session) is to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • increase awareness of the range of available climate mitigation and adaptation measures; • explore the potential contribution that different climate solutions can make; • provide participants with a framework to allow them to identify the most relevant climate solutions for their region or country. 				
Session learning outcomes		<p>On successful completion of this training module (session), participants will be able to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • prioritise potential climate mitigation and adaptation solutions relevant for farming in their region. 				
Time	Theme	Objective/key learnings/ attitudes	Activity (both for the facilitator and the participants)	Who/Facilitator and Co-facilitator	Resources/Material	Documentation
Day 2 14:55 – 15:10	climate mitigation and adaptation practices		<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Based on likelihood of implementation line, ask each participant to take their top 3 and bottom 3 solutions 2. Based on the rating of impact on the list provided, split again into four areas: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a. High likelihood of implementation (between 6 and 10) and low impact (between 1 and 5) b. Low likelihood of implementation (between 1 and 5) and low impact (between 1 and 5) c. High likelihood of implementation (between 6 and 10) and high impact (between 6 and 10) d. Low likelihood of implementation (between 1 and 5) and high impact (between 6 and 10) 3. Place in the correct place in the matrix. NB there could be the same solution in multiple boxes. 	Tom, Niamh Help will be required by other facilitators to guide each group.	Flip chart, markers, Pre-printed cards with solutions, printed impact level of the solutions list	Example of layout below (Figure 2)
Tea/coffee break						

Name of session		Prioritising climate mitigation and adaptation practices relevant for farming in your region				Activity no. 7 and 8
Time		14:30 – 15:10 and 15:25 – 15:45				
Session objective		<p>The objective(s) of this training module (session) is to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • increase awareness of the range of available climate mitigation and adaptation measures; • explore the potential contribution that different climate solutions can make; • provide participants with a framework to allow them to identify the most relevant climate solutions for their region or country. 				
Session learning outcomes		<p>On successful completion of this training module (session), participants will be able to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • prioritise potential climate mitigation and adaptation solutions relevant for farming in their region. 				
Time	Theme	Objective/key learnings/ attitudes	Activity (both for the facilitator and the participants)	Who/Facilitator and Co-facilitator	Resources/Material	Documentation
Day 2 15:25 – 15:30	climate mitigation and adaptation practices		<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Take a photo of the matrix 2. Use time during tea break to gather information 3. Participants to return to their groups 	Tom, Niamh Help will be required by other facilitators to guide each group.	Flip chart, markers, Pre-printed cards with solutions, printed impact level of the solutions list Answers to be kept from previous session as needed for this feedback session	
Day 2 15:30 – 15:45			<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 4. Feedback suggestions to present: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a) Was there agreement in the likelihood of implementation for each solution across the different stakeholders? b) Difference between impacts for each solution given by the group vs the expert opinion (the pre-printed sheet)? <p>Solutions that are in the 'High impact, Low likelihood of implementation' box?</p>			

Name of session		Barriers and solutions to the uptake of mitigation and adaptation practices (and the provision of climate advisory services)				Activity no. 9
Time		15:45 – 17:00				
Session objective		<p>The objective(s) of this training module (session) is to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> make participants aware of the pre-requisites, barriers and solutions to the uptake of potential climate mitigation and adaptation solutions relevant for farming in their region. 				
Session learning outcomes		<p>On successful completion of this training module (session), participants will be able to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> identify the necessary pre-requisites to increase the likelihood of uptake of the relevant climate solution; understand the potential barriers and identify solutions to uptake of climate mitigation and adaptation practices relevant to farming in their region. 				
Time	Theme	Objective/key learnings/attitudes	Activity (both for the facilitator and the participants)	Who/Facilitator and Co-facilitator	Resources/Material	Documentation
Day 2 15:45 – 16:10	Climate mitigation and adaptation practices	Make participants aware of the pre-requisites, barriers and solutions to the uptake of climate mitigation and adaptation practices relevant for farming in their region	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Participants to remain in their 4 groups of 10 participants Take two high impact, low uptake potential solutions from the matrix in the previous activity For a solution, each participant will write 2 pre-requisites and 2 barriers on post-its All participants to place post-its on flip chart together Facilitators to rearrange putting similar answers together Discuss and add any additional pre-requisites or barriers required Repeat until all solutions provided are discussed (or until the time allotted is finished) 	Tom, Niamh Help will be required by other facilitators to guide each group.	Flip chart, markers, Pre-printed cards with solutions, printed impact level of the solutions list Answers to be kept from previous session as needed for this feedback session	
Day 2 16:10 –16:35	Climate mitigation and adaptation practices	Make participants aware of the supports that can help increase uptake of potential climate mitigation and adaptation practices relevant to farming in their region	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Discuss ‘what support is available/can be offered’ to help farmers implement solutions to reduce GHG emissions and increase carbon sequestration e.g. training, policy, financial, technical Facilitators should try to have the supports be linked to the pre-requisites and barriers identified 	Tom, Niamh Help will be required by other facilitators to guide each group.	Flip chart, markers, Pre-printed cards with solutions, printed impact level of the solutions list Answers to be kept from previous session as needed for this feedback session	

Name of session		Barriers and solutions to the uptake of mitigation and adaptation practices (and the provision of climate advisory services)			Activity no. 9	
Time		15:45 – 17:00				
Session objective		<p>The objective(s) of this training module (session) is to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> make participants aware of the pre-requisites, barriers and solutions to the uptake of potential climate mitigation and adaptation solutions relevant for farming in their region. 				
Session learning outcomes		<p>On successful completion of this training module (session), participants will be able to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> identify the necessary pre-requisites to increase the likelihood of uptake of the relevant climate solution; understand the potential barriers and identify solutions to uptake of climate mitigation and adaptation practices relevant to farming in their region. 				
Time	Theme	Objective/key learnings/attitudes	Activity (both for the facilitator and the participants)	Who/Facilitator and Co-facilitator	Resources/Material	Documentation
Day 2 16:35 – 17:00		Feedback	<p>10. Facilitator from each group to present the main pre-requisites and barriers of each solution – keep brief</p> <p>11. Facilitator then explains what the group can offer in terms of supporting implementation</p>		Flip chart, markers, Pre-printed cards with solutions, printed impact level of the solutions list Answers to be kept from previous session as needed for this feedback session	

7.5 Storyboards for In-Person Day 3

Name of session		Energizer: Alternative use of objects				Activity no. 1
Time		09:00 – 09:15				
Session objective		The objective(s) of this training module (session) is to: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • encourage divergent and unconventional thinking. • find ideas 				
Session learning outcomes		On successful completion of this training module (session), participants will be able to: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • warm-up for the meeting • getting to know others • improve your innovative strength and problem-solving skills 				
In the remainder of the table below, list your sequential plan of action for the module (session) that will allow you to deliver on your session objective.						
Time	Theme	Objective/key learnings/attitudes	Activity (both for the facilitator and the participants)	Who/Facilitator and Co-facilitator	Resources/Material	Documentation
Day 3 09:00 – 09:15	How to start a meeting with unconventional thinking and get in touch with others	Participants are aware of how to warm up for a meeting	The facilitator explains the rule and makes the timekeeper: Each participant should write down as many ideas as possible for alternative ways of using an everyday object, such as a toothbrush. After 3 mins, each participant goes to another participant, introduces themselves and discusses the alternative use of the toothbrush. After 3 mins there is a change, then after 3 mins again.	Annelie, Ingeborg	None	None

Name of session		How change happens on farm: understanding the learning journey for both the climate smart advisor and farmer; and motivating farmers for climate action				Activity no. 3
Time		10:00 – 11:00				
Session objective		The objective(s) of this training module (session) is to: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • show how change happens on farm: understanding the learning journey for both the climate smart advisor and farmer • learn how to motivate farmers for climate action 				
Session learning outcomes		On successful completion of this training module (session), participants will be able to: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • motivate farmers • understand important points of change in the course of Climate Smart Advising 				
Time	Theme	Objective/key learnings/attitudes	Activity (both for the facilitator and the participants)	Who/Facilitator and Co-facilitator	Resources/Material	Documentation
Day 3 10.00 – 10:30	Learning journey of farmers	How change happens on farm: understanding the learning journey for both the climate smart advisor and farmer; Motivating farmers for climate action	Group : countries with 3 advisors (Germany, Spain, Poland, France, UK, Italy) = together other countries put with others in group of 5 persons in 5 groups 2 steps : first creative then a presentation of what we imagine in France second step : enrich your journey open question : advisor’s journey?	Caroline, Florence 10 groups in total = we need facilitators	erasable chalk paper board (cutting from rolls like https://www.amazon.com/chalk-paper-roll/s?k=chalk+paper+roll) pre-defined cards and empty cards	Photographs, keep paper boards and cards
Day 3 10:30 – 11:00	Exchange		Present journey to another group and listen to their journey (mixing multi-country group and “big” country)			

Name of session		The role of diagnostic tools for CoP activities				Activity no. 4
Time		11:15 – 12:30				
Session objective		The objective(s) of this training module (session) is to: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • the role of diagnostic tools • procedure for testing advisory tools through COP activities 				
Session learning outcomes		On successful completion of this training module (session), participants will be able to: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • know of a range of diagnostic tools and when they might be applicable during the CoP lifetime 				
Time	Theme	Objective/key learnings/attitudes	Activity (both for the facilitator and the participants)	Who/Facilitator and Co-facilitator	Resources/Material	Documentation
Day 3 11:15 – 11:45	Diagnostic tools	Learn about diagnostic tools and where they could be used	Add diagnostic tools to the journey elaborated in the previous session on how change happens 1. Which tools do you know of? 2. Where in the journey would you keep them and why? Make groups of 10 People each, 4 groups.	Florence, Caroline, Annelie Make sure beforehand you have one tool in each group	Screen with Journey or printed journey for each group	Keep paper sheets and make photographs
Day 3 11:45 – 12:15			Exchange of results among the groups	All		
Day 3 12:15 – 12:30			Presentation of one key tool as example (FüAk) to show video of emission calculator	FüAk		

Name of session		The potential for win: win solutions and rewarding mechanisms				Activity no. 6
Time		14:30 – 15:15				
Session objective		<p>The objective(s) of this training module (session) is to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> determine how participants perceive and start thinking about the concept of rewarding mechanisms inspire participants by presenting to them different types of reward mechanisms and benefits of climate smart consulting services 				
Session learning outcomes		<p>On successful completion of this training module (session), participants will be able to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> have a better understanding on the benefits of climate smart advisory services and are able to communicate those in a CoP/to advisors 				
Time	Theme	Objective/key learnings/attitudes	Activity (both for the facilitator and the participants)	Who/Facilitator and Co-facilitator	Resources/Material	Documentation
Day 3 14:30 – 15:15	The potential for win-win solutions and rewarding mechanisms	Participants are aware of different concepts of rewarding mechanisms and benefits of climate smart advisory services	Group exercise and presentations	Tom Schaecken	Pens and cards	Photo story, protocol etc.
Day 3 14.30 – 14:45			<p>Introduction of theme and group exercise:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> What are rewarding mechanisms in the context of climate smart advisory services according to you? What's your perception? What would different people expect (farmers, vs. public vs. advisors vs policy makers) <p>Participants get 12 minutes to discuss and write their answers with pens on cards.</p>	Tom Schaecken		
Day 3 14:45 – 15:00			<p>Presentation by Tom Schaecken with examples from Belgium (Includes different stakeholder groups (e.g. via personas) and purely economic as well as multiple benefits (societal as well) that can arise from climate smart advisory services), showing civil society projects that can arise from CSA services but also strictly economic (navigating through subsidy schemes for instance) and certificates, sustainable business models</p>	Tom Schaecken		

Name of session		The potential for win: win solutions and rewarding mechanisms				Activity no. 6
Time		14:30 – 15:15				
Session objective		The objective(s) of this training module (session) is to: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> determine how participants perceive and start thinking about the concept of rewarding mechanisms inspire participants by presenting to them different types of reward mechanisms and benefits of climate smart consulting services 				
Session learning outcomes		On successful completion of this training module (session), participants will be able to: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> have a better understanding on the benefits of climate smart advisory services and are able to communicate those in a CoP/to advisors 				
Time	Theme	Objective/key learnings/attitudes	Activity (both for the facilitator and the participants)	Who/Facilitator and Co-facilitator	Resources/Material	Documentation
14:55 – 15:10			Presentation with example by Teagasc	Tom O’Dwyer		
Day 3 15:10 – 15:15			Feedback from the audience, how presentations compare with the group work results (group work results will not be presented by each group due to time constraints), Q&A with the presenters			

Name of session		Advisory approaches: focussing on working with other AKIS actors to increase the uptake of climate solutions, including case study examples from Scotland and Ireland (presentation + network analysis)				Activity No. 7
Time		15:30 – 17:00				
Session objective		The objective(s) of this training module (session) is to: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> learn how to identify external participants for the CoP (specifically AKIS actors) 				
Session learning outcomes		On successful completion of this training module (session), participants will be able to: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> apply the network analysis in their own CoP's 				
Time	Theme	Objective/key learnings/attitudes	Activity (both for the facilitator and the participants)	Who/Facilitator and Co-facilitator	Resources/Material	Documentation
Day 3 15:30 – 15:40	Identification of external CoP participants	Develop a broad view of potential participants/supporters that otherwise would not come to mind. The Network Analysis visualises positions of involvement. Actors can be involved in different ways, and some essential links might be missing. This analysis helps to identify priorities for strengthening links.	Introduction of the Method „network analysis”: material Pinboard, cards in 4 colours	András	Pinboard coloured pens, moderation cards	Photographs
Day 3 15:40 – 16:10		Our aim is to give participants a "live" introduction to network analysis through two interviews ("celebrity interview mode")	We present a method of "network analysis" using a Scottish and an Irish example. We interview experts (Rebecca, Tom) about the initiatives (Farming for a Better Climate and the Signpost Programme). Visualise the persons/partners you need for successful implementation. The 4 roles (partners, users, suppliers, links).	András, Annelie (András talks to the interviewees, Annelie visualises the network on moderation cards)	Pinboard coloured pens, moderation cards	

Name of session		Advisory approaches: focussing on working with other AKIS actors to increase the uptake of climate solutions, including case study examples from Scotland and Ireland (presentation + network analysis)				Activity No. 7
Time		15:30 – 17:00				
Session objective		The objective(s) of this training module (session) is to: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> learn how to identify external participants for the CoP (specifically AKIS actors) 				
Session learning outcomes		On successful completion of this training module (session), participants will be able to: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> apply the network analysis in their own CoP's 				
Time	Theme	Objective/key learnings/attitudes	Activity (both for the facilitator and the participants)	Who/Facilitator and Co-facilitator	Resources/Material	Documentation
			<p>in the network analysis: 4 cards in different colours (red, blue, green, black)</p> <p>Crucial factors in the success of an initiative are represented by those who adopt different positions of involvement:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Users will benefit from the initiative. Suppliers are required to contribute. Partners feel ownership towards the initiative Links connect partners to suppliers and users. <p>Examples of questions:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> What is the „project“? What is needed? Who should be involved? What is their role? Who can make connections? Which connections should be improved? 			

Name of session		Advisory approaches: focussing on working with other AKIS actors to increase the uptake of climate solutions, including case study examples from Scotland and Ireland (presentation + network analysis)				Activity No. 7
Time		15:30 – 17:00				
Session objective		The objective(s) of this training module (session) is to: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> learn how to identify external participants for the CoP (specifically AKIS actors) 				
Session learning outcomes		On successful completion of this training module (session), participants will be able to: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> apply the network analysis in their own CoP's 				
Time	Theme	Objective/key learnings/attitudes	Activity (both for the facilitator and the participants)	Who/Facilitator and Co-facilitator	Resources/Material	Documentation
Day 3 16:10 – 16: 45			Teamwork: Hand out handout to participants We form groups of 6-7 people (6 groups). Each group should carry out a network analysis on a topic of their choice. Give topic recommendations! 25 minutes. Each group will present their network analysis in 2-3 minutes.			
Day 3 16:45 – 17:00			Reflection about the method.	Ingeborg		

Name of session		Advisory Approaches – Farming for a Better Climate case study example from Scotland				Activity no. 8 (addition)
Time		16.00 – 16.30				
Session objective		The objective(s) of this training module (session) is to: provide a case study, outlining how the Farming for a Better Climate initiative has worked with farmers to increase the knowledge of climate friendly and efficient farm practices. The case study will showcase some of the activities carried out under the project, farmer motivators for change and hidden barriers.				
Session learning outcomes		On successful completion of this training module (session), participants will be able to: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • recognise potential barriers to making climate friendly changes to routine farming practices • recognise motivators for change • hear key outcomes from the work with farmer groups on their journey towards more climate friendly practices • find additional resources that may compliment their CoP activities, aimed at a farming audience 				
Time	Theme	Objective/key learnings/attitudes	Activity (both for the facilitator and the participants)	Who/Facilitator and Co-facilitator	Resources/Material	Documentation
Day 3 16.00 – 16.30	Opportunities and Challenges for Climate Smart Advisory Services	As listed in session learning outcomes (bulleted list above)	Delivery of PPT presentation and links to project website resources; opportunity for Q's.	Rebecca Audsley (SRUC)	None; PPT delivery	If providing slide set, please offer in PDF only as speakers notes will be included in the slides.

7.6 Storyboards for In-Person Day 4

Name of session		Energizer: my North				Activity no 1
Time		9:00 – 09:15				
Session objective		The objective(s) of this training module (session) is to: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • get people energized and motivated for the last day of the TTT • get people focused on the objective of this last day (planning, monitoring and evaluation) 				
Session learning outcomes		On successful completion of this training module (session), participants will be able to: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • start the last day of the TTT with motivation and focus • understand the importance of team alignment 				
In the remainder of the table below, list your sequential plan of action for the module (session) that will allow you to deliver on your session objective.						
Time	Theme	Objective/key learnings/attitudes	Activity (both for the facilitator and the participants)	Who/Facilitator and Co-facilitator	Resources/Material	Documentation
Day 4 09:00 – 09:15	Energizer: “My North”	Get participants energized and focused for the day	This activity is done in a big room with all participants together. <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. ask the group to stand up, leaving enough space between them (everyone should be able to stretch their arms out to the side without touching anyone or anything). 2. show the team where north is (this could actually be north if you have a compass on your phone, but you can make it up!) 3. tell everyone to cover their eyes with their left hand and turn ten times, covering their eyes the whole time 4. when they have finished, ask everyone to hold out their arm and point to where they think north is now (their eyes should still be closed). 5. the team can then open their eyes to recognise the many different directions people are pointing in 	Annelie All participants	None	None

Name of session		Guidelines for CSA Training Seminars and Events				Activity no. 2
Time		09:15 – 09:45				
Session objective		<p>The objective(s) of this training module (session) is to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> provide guidelines for delivery of training event/seminars to be delivered as part of the 8 CoP meetings per CoP 				
Session learning outcomes		<p>On successful completion of this training module (session), participants will be able to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> recognise the minimum timeline for planning a seminar or training event provide a guide to planning their event, either as a classroom-based activity or on-farm training understand the project administrative requirements which must be completed as part of the training event signpost/provide link to the written guidelines and checklists 				
Time	Theme	Objective/key learnings/attitudes	Activity (both for the facilitator and the participants)	Who/Facilitator and Co-facilitator	Resources/Material	Documentation
Day 4 09.45 – 10.15	Planning, monitoring and beyond the CoP	As listed in session learning outcomes (bulleted list above)	Delivery of Ppt presentation and links to project tools to support administrative requirements; opportunity for Q's.	Rebecca Audsley (SRUC)	PPT delivery; Printed document (guidelines and checklists)	If providing slide set, please offer in PDF only as speakers notes will be included in the slides.

Name of session		How will you know that the COP is functioning well?: monitoring progress				Activity no.3
Time		09:45 – 11:00				
Session objective		<p>The objective(s) of this training module (session) is to</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> introduce the aspect and purpose of ME &L in a COP to future trainers get people to think and work around the concept of “progress” in a creative and participatory way to equip participants with the three ME&L tools (Dynamic Learning Agenda) and a concrete schedule for ME&L 				
Session learning outcomes		<p>On successful completion of this training module (session), participants will be able to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> leave the TTT with a concrete plan and tool how to monitor progress throughout the COP lifetime dive into the next session on “Making a first COP Plan”, also based on what they learned in this session 				
Time	Theme	Objective/key learnings/attitudes	Activity (both for the facilitator and the participants)	Who/Facilitator and Co-facilitator	Resources/Material	Documentation
Day 4 09:45 – 09:55	ME&L: purpose	To enhance capacity development within the CoP’s, we actively monitor and evaluate the CoP functioning and the capacity development and document lessons learned about to the delivery of effective and targeted climate-smart advice.	Introduce the purpose and goal of ME&L in CSA. WP4 has developed 3 tools for this, which will be covered in this session. Central question of ME&L in CSA: What works when and how to strengthen the role of advisory services to realise Climate Smart Agriculture?	Jorieke	PPT	Photographs
Day 4 09:55 – 10:15	ME&L tools for CoP’s	Introduction of the 3 ME&L tools to be used in/by the CoP’s, covering 1) What it is; and 2) How it serves the CoP’s. The three tools:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> CoP evaluation: to evaluate and monitor experiences in the CoP’s CSA Capacity Assessment Tool (CSA-CAT): to monitor the development of capacity of CSA Dynamic learning agenda (DLA): to structure and coordinate learning within and between CoP’s 	Jorieke		
Day 4 10:15 – 10:40	Using the tools in your CoP		<p>Explain how the CSC use the three tools in their CoP’s</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> CoP evaluation using a survey -> initiated by WP4 CSA-CAT: online assessment, CSC asks all CoP participants to full in the tool DLA: include in your CoP plans, then continuously learn throughout the CoP 	Jorieke		

Name of session		How will you know that the COP is functioning well?: monitoring progress				Activity no.3
Time		09:45 – 11:00				
Session objective		<p>The objective(s) of this training module (session) is to</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> introduce the aspect and purpose of ME &L in a COP to future trainers get people to think and work around the concept of “progress” in a creative and participatory way to equip participants with the three ME&L tools (Dynamic Learning Agenda) and a concrete schedule for ME&L 				
Session learning outcomes		<p>On successful completion of this training module (session), participants will be able to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> leave the TTT with a concrete plan and tool how to monitor progress throughout the COP lifetime dive into the next session on “Making a first COP Plan”, also based on what they learned in this session 				
Time	Theme	Objective/key learnings/attitudes	Activity (both for the facilitator and the participants)	Who/Facilitator and Co-facilitator	Resources/Material	Documentation
			<p>wave. New questions come up? Or can you share lessons learned? Add them to the DLA!</p> <p>Reiterate timing: CoP evaluation: Annual CSA-Capacity Assessment Tool: Annual DLA: continuous during CoP waves</p>			
Day 4 10:40 – 11:00	DLA Exercise	Commit CoP’s to DLA/create ownership; the goal is to learn within a CoP, but also between CoP’s and exchange lessons learned as a project as a whole	Instruct CSC to incorporate the DLA in their CoP plans. No time to go into it in depth, but scroll through the DLA and instruct the CSC to add their CoP to learning questions. Connect DLA Learning question to CoP plan	Jorieke		

Name of session		Creating a CoP plan				Activity no. 4
Time		11:15 – 12:30				
Session objective		<p>The objective(s) of this training module (session) is to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> provide the CSC's with a clear outline of the process and practical experience to enable them to develop the CoP Plan at the first CoP meeting in a participatory manner 				
Session learning outcomes		<p>On successful completion of this training module (session), participants will be able to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> plan the CoP activities and develop the CoP Plan 				
Time	Theme	Objective/key learnings/attitudes	Activity (both for the facilitator and the participants)	Who/Facilitator and Co-facilitator	Resources/Material	Documentation
Day 4 11:15 – 11:30	Creating the CoP plan	Making participants aware of the necessity to plan the CoP activities and to develop the CoP plan	<p>Short presentation about</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> The types of activities in the Cop (obligatory vs discretionary) plus examples The freedom to select or adapt the activities to suit the CoP CoP Plan CoP Planning exercise instructions 		Presentation	CSA presentation
Day 4 11:30 – 12:30	Creating the CoP plan	Understanding, and hands-on experience of the process of CoP Plan development so it can be applied at the first CoP meeting.	Participants work in groups of 5-6 CSC and are tasked with selecting the activities and formulating the CoP plan for a fictional CoP (either focused on CSC collaboration or other fictional topic).		<p>Printed CoP activity planning exercise:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> CoP Activity stickers CoP Activity cards CoP activity planning template 	CSA CoP Plan template

8 Appendices

8.1 TTT Monitoring, Evaluation and Learning Process

The purpose of evaluating the CSA Train the Trainers event is, on the one hand, to follow the development of the training and the participants during the training days, and on the other hand, to evaluate the effectiveness of training and harvest valuable feedback in order to improve for the next version of the TTT. In designing these evaluation tools a balance was struck between getting the appropriate level of insights and not demanding too much time and effort of the participants. Three simple-to-use tools will be used:

- end of the day evaluation per session;
- light reflection questions at the end of the day; and
- overall evaluation of the TTT.

Together these three evaluation tools provide space for feedback as the TTT progresses, gives an impression of the effectiveness of the TTT and valuable input for further strengthening the TTT and more in general the support to the Climate Smart Coaches. Below each of these instruments are explained.

1. End of the day evaluation per session

This tool primarily serves the improvement of the different parts of the training. It consists of the same straightforward simple questions for each day and will be used in printed form. At the beginning of the training the form is introduced. Each day the participants receive the evaluation form in the morning. They are invited to fill it out directly after each session. At the end of the day participants will be reminded and given some time at the end of each day to complete and submit the form. This takes no longer than 5-10 minutes. The main question is:

How do you evaluate the different sessions on today’s training agenda, in terms of both content and methods?

A simple 1-5 Likert scale (1= poor and 5 =great)

Session	Content (1-5)	Method (1-5)	Suggestions for improvement

2. Light reflection questions at the end of the day

The purpose is to open the space for feedback from the participants, and for the trainers to understand the general atmosphere in the group and what needs attention on the subsequent training days. The questions below are asked in Menti, so results are visible to all. Depending on time and energy, the facilitator may invite participants to share their perspective or experiences.

1. How do you generally feel after this training day? Scale 1-5 (with funny pictures)

This question allows participants to check in and express their overall feeling about the training and their current state in a fun and visual way.

2. What did you learn today? Open question.

Participants can provide valuable feedback on what resonated with them the most, and it can be inspiring to see what others have learned.

3. What are burning issues/questions that need our attention in the next day/period? Open question.

This question allows participants to express any pressing issues or questions they have that they feel need to be addressed in the following day's training sessions.

3. Overall Evaluation for the entire TTT

This is the overall evaluation of the training for the purpose of understanding the effectiveness and gathering input for future training events. The questions below will be presented in an online survey at the end of the training days. It should take the participants no more than 15 minutes to complete the survey.

1. Training Content

- a. How do you rate the relevance of the training content for your role and responsibilities as a Climate Smart Coach (1 being poor, 5 being perfectly relevant)?
- b. Which of the following aspects could receive more or less attention during the TTT?
 - Technical CSF content: less – same – more (optional please specify)
 - CS advisory methods: less – same – more (optional please specify)
 - CSC role and CoP facilitation methods, less – same – more (optional please specify)

2. Trainer Effectiveness

- a. How would you rate the knowledge and expertise of the trainers?
- b. How did you experience the trainers' ability to engage participants and facilitate discussions?
- c. Any suggestions for improvement ...

3. Training Methodology

- a. Rate in general the effectiveness of the training methods used.
- b. How do you appreciate the balance between theory and practice?
- c. What suggestions do you have to further improve the training methods?

4. Learning Outcomes

- a. To what extent did the training help you better **understand** climate change and climate-smart practices?
- b. To what extent did the training contribute to your advisory **skills** for climate smart advise?
- c. How confident do you feel in **applying** the training content in your advisory practice?
- d. How confident do you feel in **facilitating learning and exchange** in your CoP?

5. Overall Satisfaction

- a. How satisfied are you overall with the training event?
- a. Can you rank the following aspects of the training in order of importance:
 - The content on climate change
 - The content on climate smart farming
 - The content on climate smart advise methods
 - The content on facilitation skills
 - Information about CSA project and CoP's
 - Exchange with other CSC, topics and regions

6. Suggestions for Improvement (Open questions)

- a. How can the training be improved? Please share any ideas for improvement
- b. What specific topics or areas would you like to see covered in future training events?
- c. What specific skills would you like to be trained in during future training events?
- d. What would further support you to strengthen your confidence as a Climate Smart Coach?

7. Additional Comments

- a. Please share any additional comments or feedback about the training event.

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